

Template - Processing analysis

Template to process all surfaces acquired with the LSM with the 50x/0.75 and 50x/0.95 objectives.

Processing

Identity card			
Name:	Kremasti4_LSM_50x_natural_b_Topo		
Created on:	4/15/2021 10:51:24 AM		
Studiabile type:	Surface		
Axis:	X		
Length:	255.5	μm	
Size:	3000	points	
Spacing:	85.19	nm	
Axis:	Y		
Length:	255.5	μm	
Size:	3000	points	
Spacing:	85.19	nm	
Axis:	Z		
Layer type:	Topography		
Length:	49.89	μm	
Size:	65532	digits	
Spacing:	0.7613	nm	
NM-points ratio:	0.000 % (0 Pts)		

Identity card			
Name:	Kremasti4_LSM_50x...filtered (λ s 2.500 μm)		
File path:	D:\...\Kremasti4_LSM_50x_natural_b_Topo.sur		
Created on:	4/15/2021 10:51:24 AM		
Studiabile type:	Surface		
Axis:	X		
Length:	255.5	μm	
Size:	3000	points	
Spacing:	85.19	nm	
Offset:	0.000	μm	
Axis:	Y		
Length:	255.5	μm	
Size:	3000	points	
Spacing:	85.19	nm	
Offset:	-255.5	μm	
Axis:	Z		
Layer type:	Topography		
Length:	22.92	μm	
Min:	-12.47	μm	
Max:	10.45	μm	
Size:	301067	digits	
Spacing:	0.07613	nm	
NM-points ratio:	20.65 % (1858103 Pts)		

Identity card			
Name:	Kremasti4_LSM_50x_na...in non-measured points		
Created on:	4/15/2021 10:51:24 AM		
Studiable type:	Surface		
Axis: X			
Length:	255.5	μm	
Size:	3000	points	
Spacing:	85.19	nm	
Axis: Y			
Length:	255.5	μm	
Size:	3000	points	
Spacing:	85.19	nm	
Axis: Z			
Layer type:	Topography		
Length:	22.92	μm	
Size:	301067	digits	
Spacing:	0.07613	nm	
NM-points ratio:	0.000 % (0 Pts)		

Analyses

8. ISO 25178-2 parameters on surface #7

ISO 25178 - Primary surface			
<i>F: [Workflow] Form removed (LS-poly 3)</i>			
<i>S-filter (λs): [Workflow] S-filtered (λs 2.500 μm)</i>			
Height parameters			
Sq	4.090	μm	
Ssk	-0.3915		
Sku	2.527		
Sp	10.44	μm	
Sv	12.48	μm	
Sz	22.92	μm	
Sa	3.403	μm	
Functional parameters			
Smr	0.2389	%	
Smc	4.565	μm	
Sxp	9.020	μm	
Spatial parameters			
Sal	32.43	μm	
Str	*****		
Std	93.24	°	
Hybrid parameters			
Sdq	0.6585		
Sdr	15.94	%	
Functional parameters (Volume)			
Vm	0.1529	$\mu\text{m}^3/\mu\text{m}^2$	
Vv	4.718	$\mu\text{m}^3/\mu\text{m}^2$	
Vmp	0.1529	$\mu\text{m}^3/\mu\text{m}^2$	
Vmc	4.142	$\mu\text{m}^3/\mu\text{m}^2$	
Vvc	4.240	$\mu\text{m}^3/\mu\text{m}^2$	
Vvv	0.4776	$\mu\text{m}^3/\mu\text{m}^2$	

Analyses:	
ISO 25178	8.
Furrow	9.
Texture direction	10.
Texture isotropy	11.
SSFA	12.

Warnings

Str: The autocorrelation lobe touches the edges. Try to level the...

9. Furrow analysis on surface #7

All furrows are shown.

Parameters	Value	Unit
Maximum depth of furrows	10.88	µm
Mean depth of furrows	3.135	µm
Mean density of furrows	3056	cm/cm2

10. Texture direction on surface #7

Parameters	Value	Unit
First direction	90.01	°
Second direction	135.0	°
Third direction	45.00	°

11. Texture isotropy on surface #7

Parameters	Value	Unit
Texture isotropy	82.67	%

12. SSFA on surface #7

